

The Hustle Trap: How Hustle Culture Warps
Gen Z's Mental Health and Success Mindset

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In today's high school, the concept of "hustle culture" has become a pervasive yet often unspoken issue. Hustle culture glorifies overworking, constant productivity, and personal sacrifice as signs of ambition and success. However, for students, this mindset is increasingly tied to chronic stress, anxiety, and burnout. To understand the scope of this issue, a survey was distributed to high school students across all high school grade levels, capturing data on academic pressure, extracurricular involvement, work obligations, perceived mental health, etc. With over 200 anonymous responses from students of varying backgrounds, the data reveals alarming trends tied to gender, race, academic load, and expectations. Hustle culture is a structural issue that undermines student well-being.

Students across all grade levels report high levels of stress, with freshmen surprisingly reporting the highest average stress level (7.12 out of 10), followed by sophomores (6.61), juniors (6.57), and seniors (4.67). This suggests that academic pressure begins early, even before students take on the full load of advanced courses. For example, 47.06% of freshmen respondents indicated feeling pressure from teachers, and 61.76% from parents, with 61.76% saying they often feel they are falling behind. While juniors and sophomores still bear heavy workloads, the decline among seniors may reflect disengagement or even adaptation to pressure. These findings challenge the assumption that stress peaks during junior year alone and indicate a systemic issue that builds from the beginning of high school.

Although both male and female students experience academic pressure, female students overwhelmingly reported higher levels of internalized stress. Among female respondents, 53.55% reported feeling guilty when taking breaks, and 74.19% agreed or strongly agreed that they feel pressure to be productive even in their free time. 56.13% of female students reported feeling behind even when staying on top of their tasks, compared to 38% of male students. This

aligns with national data showing that girls often internalize pressure to succeed academically and socially. The guilt associated with taking breaks is a key feature of hustle culture, and it disproportionately affects female students, leading to anxiety, perfectionism, and sleep deprivation.

Racial and cultural backgrounds play a role in how students experience hustle culture and stress. Students identifying as “Asian, Indian” reported the highest average stress level at 9.0, followed by “South Asian” students at 8.0 and “Middle Eastern or North African” students at 7.33. Asian students overall reported an average stress level of 6.75, compared to 6.60 for Black students and 6.49 for White students. 67.19% of Asian students selected more than one source of pressure, often including social media, teachers, and peers, indicating that their experience of pressure has multiple components. The data underscores the need for culturally responsive mental health support that acknowledges these added pressures and dismantles one-size-fits-all support systems.

The number of AP, honors, or advanced classes students take strongly correlates with stress levels. Of the students taking five or more advanced classes, 39.39% reported doing at least three hours of homework a night, with 18.18% exceeding four hours. Many of these students also reported sleeping only 4–5 hours a night and feeling "guilty" for resting. Students in the 3–4 AP range reported slightly less stress, but still showed elevated guilt and pressure scores. The survey also showed that 36.36% of those in the 5+ AP group felt that hustle culture has negatively impacted their mental health. Hustle culture tells students that success is directly proportional to how busy they are.

Involvement in 2–4 extracurriculars was most common among respondents (47%), and 33% were involved in 4 or more. Of those with part-time jobs (19% of respondents), the majority reported sleeping less than six hours a night. Nearly all respondents balancing jobs and 3+ extracurriculars rated their stress at a 7 or higher, with many citing burnout and lack of free time. Notably, 64% of students with jobs also reported falling asleep in class or struggling to stay awake. These findings reinforce that hustle culture isn't confined to academics; students are stretching themselves thin across multiple areas and sacrificing sleep and mental health for the sake of productivity.

The majority of students identified themselves (87.5%), teachers (53.8%), parents (53.8%), and social media (23.9%) as sources of pressure. 41% also included friends and peers. This shows that hustle culture is not simply a school problem; it's a systemic issue reinforced at home, online, and in social settings. For example, students mentioned feeling the need to present themselves as busy and successful on social media, even when struggling. One student said, "I feel like I have to prove I'm doing something all the time or people will think I'm lazy." This pressure to appear accomplished, even outside academic contexts, deepens the mental strain.

When asked if "always doing more, staying busy, etc, hurt your mental health", 68% of students said "Yes" or "Somewhat." More than 76% said they felt guilty taking breaks, even when tired or overwhelmed. Additionally, students with higher AP loads and extracurriculars consistently reported feelings of burnout, emotional exhaustion, and hopelessness. One student responded, "I see the top of a mountain as perfection, and I work so hard to reach it (climbing, stumbling, falling back, but always pushing forward). Yet on the rare occasion I actually make it to the top, I look around and notice another mountain, taller and steeper. Maybe it's mine, maybe it's someone else's. And suddenly, all the effort I put in feels small. I forget the climb, forget the

struggle, and all I can feel is that I've fallen short." Another shared, "It hurts, and it's extremely painful. The pressure to think you're not good enough and that the world will explode. And even if the parents or school says "it's fine it's just one grade"- it literally isn't. It determines whether you will be happy or sad for the rest of the week ESPECIALLY if you're a student who is trying to balance anything and a student who feels the pressure to succeed." These stories are not outliers, they're representative of the majority.

This data paints an evident picture: hustle culture is deeply embedded in school environments, affecting students from every background. But it is not inevitable. Schools must shift the narrative away from overachievement and toward sustainable success. Schools need to stop treating mental health as an optional add-on and start making it part of the classroom experience, with lessons that teach balance, emotional regulation, and self-awareness. Departments should coordinate so students don't have multiple tests on the same day, and allow "relief days" during heavy weeks, just like IEP accommodations. Though Illinois offers five mental health days per year, many students don't know they exist, so schools must publicize them and consider asynchronous days to help students recharge. Teachers should also be trained to spot hidden stress, especially in high-achieving students, and shift their focus from just grades to effort, growth, and balance.

Lastly, students were asked, "Is there anything you wish schools or adults understood better about student pressure or hustle culture?" This is what some responded with:

"This is not an individual failing but a systemic failing. There is a need for more recognition of our student's health issues caused by overproductivity." -Senior at Neuqua Valley High School

“The 'golden child' who always gets straight As and 100% on all the tests isn't always okay. As someone who is seen by their peers and parents as the student who can do no wrong, I can attest to the fact that we often struggle with insecurity, perfectionism, and putting needless amounts of pressure on ourselves to do better than okay, to do better than well. The "super-nerd" who seems to only have a life inside of school, the kids who worry and fret over getting a 96% on their final assignment, the kids who beat themselves up internally for half a point taken off the extra credit portion of the test, these aren't the kids who need to be teased and called selfish, greedy, shallow, or perfectionists. These are the kids who, on purpose or by accident, did something great as a young kid. These are the kids who, when they did that thing, their parents told them they were amazing and special. These were the kids who formed the mistaken belief while still young that their parents' love, affection, and attention depended solely on achieving great things, on being the best. As the oldest of five children and the professed "golden child", I haven't lived the beautiful life that people think I have. My brothers don't like me because they don't measure up, and our parents compare them to me. My parents ignore me most often, because I'm the good one, I'm the golden child and I can handle it. I want people (grownups and kids alike) to understand that sometimes the kids who look the most put-together are actually struggling internally with no outlet to manage their stress, the ones who have inextricably tied their self-worth to the letters in the grade book and don't know how to stop it.” -Sophomore at Waubonsie Valley High School

“That we dont want to feel pressured and it is not something that is easy because if you just miss one day to fix your mental health it is actually going to end up ruining your whole week because you're playing catch up.” -Freshman at Neuqua Valley High School

“The stereotypes about mental health (it's only real if it's visible, it's only real if the student shows extreme signs). I wish they also understood how just because a lot of kids are "over average" that means if a student isn't they just immediately ignore or give up on the student.”

-Freshman at Neuqua Valley High School

“I wish adults would understand that our home environment plays a big role in student pressure or hustle culture. Some adults don't realize that their absence from their student's life takes a toll on the educational productivity.” -Sophomore at Waubonsie Valley High School

“Pressure is more often indirect, picked up from observations of peers or implied necessity to do certain things. Telling someone not to compare themselves to another isn't a solution and rarely scratches the surface of the problem.” -Junior at Neuqua Valley High School

DATA REFERENCE

Grade	Number of Students
Sophomore	116
Junior	111
Freshman	34
Senior	3

High school	Number of Students
Neuqua Valley High School	192
Waubonsie Valley High School	63
Metea Valley High School	9

Gender	Number of Students
Female	155
Male	100
Prefer not to say	5
Non-binary	4

AP, Honors, or Advanced Classes	Number of Students
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1-2	110
3-4	72
0	49
5+	33

Average Hours of Studying Each Night	Number of Students
Less than 1 hour	78
1-2 hours	135
3-4 hours	43
5+ hours	8

Average Hours of Homework Each Night	Number of Students
Less than 1 hour	39
1-2 hours	140
3-4 hours	70
5+ hours	10

Part-Time Job	Number of Students
No	171
Yes	93

Extracurriculars	Number of Students
2-3	132
4+	70
1	46
none	16

Productivity Pressure Level	Number of Students
Agree	118
Strongly agree	66
Neutral	60
Disagree	15
Strongly Disagree	5

Mental Health Harm	Number of Students
Somewhat	112
No	84
Yes	68

Feels Behind when Productive	Number of Students
Yes	129
Sometimes	97
No	38

Feels Guilty when Taking Breaks/Rest	Number of Students
Yes	123
Sometimes	78
No	63

Hours of Sleep Each Night	Number of Students
Less than 4 hours	9
4-5 hours	71
6-7 hours	166
8+ hours	18

Productivity over well-being	Number of Students
Agree	110
Strongly agree	63
Neutral	69
Disagree	14
Strongly Disagree	8

On a scale of 1–10, how stressed do you feel on a regular school week?

264 responses

Where do you feel most of this pressure comes from? (Select all that apply.)

264 responses

What is your race or ethnicity? (Check all that apply.)

264 responses

